

CURRENT ISSUES OF TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES IN MODERN EDUCATION

Avazbekova Shakhsanam Nurmamat qizi

Namangan State University lecturer

ABSTRACT

In this article, the current issues of teaching Natural Sciences in the direction of primary education, pedagogical approaches to the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching science, mechanisms for the use of educational tools, natural sciences are covered by educational goals organized in series within the Department.

Key words: Natural Sciences, pedagogical approach, pedagogical technology, educational tool, educational goals, educational quality, methodological system, audiovisual-diapositives, scientific problem.

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ НАУК В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Авазбекова Шохсанам Нурмаматовна

Преподаватель Наманганского государственного университета

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье освещаются актуальные вопросы преподавания естественных наук в области начального образования, педагогические подходы к использованию педагогических технологий в преподавании естественных наук, механизмы использования средств обучения, цели обучения, последовательно организуемые в рамках отдела естественных наук.

Ключевые слова: естественные науки, педагогический подход, педагогическая технология, средство обучения, цели обучения, качество образования, методическая система, аудиовизуальные-диапозитивы, научная проблема.

Natural sciences are a methodological system for introducing young students to the outside world in the direction of Primary Education. It includes the interconnected purpose, principles, content, methods, tools and forms of education in the field of studying the surrounding world.

Multivariativity of approaches to the interpretation of the concept of “teaching methodology” in modern education. The method is as a synthetic formation. In the modern methodology of teaching "Natural Sciences" is characterized by a wide variety of teaching methods. The choice of teaching methods, their combination in the educational process in the teaching of Natural Sciences is of fundamental importance. In the study of nature, the diversity of oral methods of teaching science is important, with problematic and programmed elements of learning, modern trends, traditional methods of using methods of teaching Natural Sciences. Currently, one of the pressing issues is modeling, technology and its uniqueness in traditional and developing educational systems, taking into account visual methods in the development of the world around them due to the demand of the period, practical methods of teaching science, types of laboratory experiments and the sequence of their complication from Grades 1 to 4.

When teaching subjects of natural sciences, students are introduced to various natural objects and processes, most of which schoolchildren cannot observe in the surrounding nature. To formulate complete and correct ideas and concepts about these objects, it is necessary to use various educational tools, for example, collections, herbarium, tables, maps.

V. F. Zuyev spoke about the importance of the use of visual educational tools in the educational process in the Natural Sciences in the XVIII century. Later, A. L. Gerd, L. S. Sevruck, V. P. Vakhterov, S. A. Pavlović, I. P. Yagodovsky, M. N. Prominent Methodist scholars such as Skatkin have reflected in their works on the role and relevance of visual learning tools in introducing children to nature. The research of modern psychologists, didacts and Methodists, in particular, L. V. Zankova, V. P. Head, N. G. Konobeevsky, G. F. Suvorova has proven that the use of visual aids increases the quality of education, contributes to the formation of cognitive interest in nature and educational science.

The presence of various educational tools requires their classification. Several of them have been developed in the methodology, for example: oral-textbooks, textbooks for students; natural-collections, herbariums, living things; images of objects and natural phenomena: flat-tables, pictures, maps; volumetric-models, dolls; audiovisual-diapositives, films, banners, films and Video Films, sound recordings have been developed. At present, these training tools are required to be improved in accordance with the Times.

Also, pedagogy in the teaching of Natural Sciences should be carried out on the basis of several pedagogical approaches to the use of technology:

- create conditions for trusting relationships and cooperation;

- planning and using collaborative and independent research methods to find solutions to scientific problems;
- development of differentiated tasks taking into account the individual abilities and age characteristics of students;
- Organization of individual and group work for the study of scientific problems;
- create conditions for working in a group, where each student can perform different images to help achieve success in a group;
- creating motivational problem situations to develop students' ability to express and argue their ideas and thoughts when answering questions, advancing hypotheses and suggestions to find solutions;
- mental attack on a specific topic to solve the problem. Each student puts forward their own ideas, which are discussed by the whole class during the analysis of the problem in order to make the right decision;
- creating problem situations in a lesson that requires research, experiments, work with resources and other types of work to find a solution;
- maintaining the interest of the reader by independently choosing the subject of the study, planning it and presenting the results;
- review and application of different types of assessment in the classroom, taking into account the criteria for awarding points.

Teachers must support the implementation of trilingual policies by helping students develop language skills. To support the study of the subject's content, teachers develop a subject-specific academic language in students. In this regard, the linguistic goals of each lesson are determined, for example, "students must associate images of animals with their names in writing and orally". Teachers are required to focus students' attention on the use of academic language, as well as help students assess their achievement in language acquisition. At the same time, teachers should support an organized and systematic language, which involves the use of useful phrases for dialogue/writing to form a rich academic language in the student.

Content on the topic is organized by educational departments. The sections are then divided into sub-sections containing the educational goals by class in the form of expected results: skill or skill, knowledge or understanding. Within each sub-department, sequentially organized learning goals allow teachers to plan their work and assess student achievement, as well as inform them about further stages of teaching (Table 1).

№	Sections sub-sections	Sub-sections
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1	I am a researcher	1.1. The role of Science and researchers
		1.2. Methods of knowing nature
2	Wildlife	2.1. Plants
		2.2. Animals
		2.3. Man
3	Substances and their properties	3.1. Types of substances
		3.2. Air
		3.3. Water
		3.4. Natural resources
4	Earth and space	4.1 place
		4.2. Kosmos
		4.3 space and time
5	Physics of nature	5.1. Forces and action
		5.2 light
		5.3. Voice
		5.4.Heat
		5.5 electricity
		5.6. Magnetism

1- table. Natural sciences are sequentially organized within the Department for educational purposes

In conclusion, it can be noted that in the course of the lesson, the teacher becomes the organizer of the cognitive activity of his students from the communicator of ready-made knowledge: from a reputable source of information, the teacher acts as a partner, coach, consultant, organizer of independent activities of streamers in the research, creative process.

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